

Anticaries Efficacy of Non-Fluoridated Dentifrice and Mouthwashes Used in Children: A Systematic Review

Mriganka Kumar Phukan*, Mousumi Goswami, Sandhya, Ajay Khanna

Department Of Paediatric and Preventive Dentistry, I.T.S Dental College, Hospital and research centre, Greater Noida

ABSTRACT

This systematic review evaluates the anticaries efficacy of non-fluoridated dentifrices and mouthrinses in children during the mixed dentition period. The study was registered in PROSPERO (CRD42024622737). A comprehensive search of PubMed, Google Scholar, The Cochrane Library, Embase, and Web of Science was conducted. In vivo randomized controlled trials (RCTs) published between 2010 and 2024 assessing the efficacy of chlorhexidine, casein phosphopeptide-amorphous calcium phosphate (CPP-ACP), xylitol, arginine, hydroxyapatite, and probiotics in non-fluoridated dentifrices and mouthrinses were included. Of 2,381 screened articles, eight studies met the inclusion criteria, assessing 2,785 children aged 6–15 years, with study durations ranging from baseline to two years. Outcomes measured included caries count, bacterial colony count, and plaque/salivary pH. Hydroxyapatite showed superior bacterial reduction compared to fluoride. Probiotic mouthrinses were as effective as fluoridated mouthrinses. Chlorhexidine significantly reduced bacterial levels, with enhanced effects when combined with fluoride. Non-fluoridated agents demonstrated comparable effectiveness to fluoride-based products. However, most research focuses on in vitro studies or primary dentition. Further randomized controlled trials are needed for children aged six and above to establish long-term efficacy.

Keywords: Non-fluoridated dentifrices, non-fluoridated mouthrinse, prevention of dental caries in children, anticaries efficacy.

INTRODUCTION

Dental caries is a multifactorial, transmissible oral disease caused by the interaction of cariogenic biofilm with fermentable carbohydrates over time (Gopikrishna, V. (Ed.). (2013). *Sturdevant's art and science of operative dentistry - South Asian edition* (1st ed.). Elsevier. ISBN: 978-81-312-3402-0). The earliest sign of enamel caries is an incipient lesion, where minerals are lost beneath the surface while the outer layer remains intact (1). Caries development is influenced by the balance between saliva and plaque, microbial community changes, and alterations in the mineral composition of enamel, primarily hydroxyapatite, making teeth more prone to decay (2). Demineralization occurs when pH drops below 5.5, leading to the loss of hydroxyl and phosphate ions from enamel due to an acidic environment. Remineralization, on the other hand, restores lost

minerals, helping maintain tooth integrity. Repeated exposure to acidic foods and poor oral hygiene disrupts this balance, resulting in early enamel lesions which can progress into cavities. Since enamel lacks cellular repair mechanisms, caries prevention and reversal rely on physiochemical interactions at the plaque-tooth interface (3). One approach to halting lesion progression involves using remineralizing agents, many of which are incorporated into dentifrices and mouthrinses.

A dentifrice is a semi-solid substance formulated to remove deposits from teeth, typically used with a toothbrush (4). These formulations contain key ingredients to promote oral health. Fluoride has long been the primary remineralizing agent used in caries prevention (5,6). Enamel is mainly composed of hydroxyapatite crystals, which fluoride can integrate into, forming fluorohydroxyapatite a stronger, more

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

acid-resistant structure. Studies suggest 1000 ppm fluoride is effective for caries prevention, though for children under six, fluoride concentrations below 500 ppm are recommended (7). According to the AAPD, children under three should use a smear (0.1 mg) of fluoridated toothpaste, while those aged three to six should limit usage to a pea-sized amount (0.25 mg) (8). Young children are prone to swallowing toothpaste, increasing the risk of dental fluorosis, a condition resulting from excessive fluoride intake during tooth development. Reports indicate that over 20,000 fluoride ingestion cases are recorded annually, with most occurring in children under six. The toxic dose is approximately 5 mg/kg of body weight, and ingestion in excess can lead to gastrointestinal distress, seizures, or, in extreme cases, fatal outcomes (8,9). Fluoride has limited effects on subsurface lesions (3). To address concerns about fluorosis and improve remineralization, alternative non-fluoridated agents have been introduced in dentifrices.

Hydroxyapatite, the primary mineral in human bones and teeth, is a key ingredient in fluoride-free dentifrices. It is biocompatible, non-toxic when swallowed, and has been extensively used in bone healing and dental implant applications. Synthetic nano-hydroxyapatite has an enhanced surface-to-volume ratio, allowing it to penetrate demineralized enamel more effectively (9). CPP-ACP, derived from milk protein, has demonstrated effectiveness in remineralizing subsurface enamel lesions. It provides a stable reservoir of free calcium and phosphate ions, maintaining mineral saturation on the enamel surface. Research suggests CPP-ACP also has antimicrobial properties, reducing the adherence of cariogenic bacteria like *S. mutans* (11). Through continuous deposition of calcium and phosphate, there is formation of hydroxyl-carbonate apatite, closely resembling biological apatite in both structure and composition (12). Arginine, an amino acid found in saliva, is metabolized by arginolytic bacteria to produce ammonia, increasing oral pH, enhances fluoride uptake, inhibit *S. mutans*, and promote the growth of beneficial bacteria like *S. sanguinis* (13).

Since young children may struggle with effective toothbrushing, mouthrinses can serve as a supplementary oral care measure. Chlorhexidine, a widely used non-fluoridated antimicrobial agent,

exhibits both bacteriostatic and bactericidal properties. While effective in reducing plaque and bacterial colonization, its long-term use is limited by side effects such as tooth staining and altered taste perception (4,14). Chitosan, a natural polysaccharide derived from crustaceans, has gained attention for its antibacterial and bio-adhesive properties. It does not promote bacterial resistance and is biodegradable, making it a promising ingredient in mouthrinses (15). Probiotics are also emerging as a beneficial component in oral care products. These live microorganisms help maintain a healthy microbial balance in the oral cavity by inhibiting harmful bacteria. As they consist of commensal flora, probiotics have not been linked to antibiotic resistance or adverse effects (16). Xylitol stands out among sugar alcohols due to its unique property of being unfermentable by oral microorganisms. This characteristic renders it a cariostatic agent as it can impede carbohydrate metabolism in various oral microorganisms. Moreover, xylitol demonstrates a distinctive inhibitory effect on glycolysis (4,16). While several studies have compared fluoridated and non-fluoridated agents, most have focused on children with primary dentition (17,18), leaving a gap in research regarding their effectiveness during the mixed dentition phase. Concerns over dental fluorosis and fluoride toxicity have led to increased interest in alternative remineralizing agents. This systematic review aims to evaluate the efficacy of non-fluoridated dentifrices and mouthrinses in children during the mixed dentition stage, addressing a crucial gap in existing literature.

2. METHODS

2.1. Study Design

A systematic review was conducted, and this paper was written according to the updated PRISMA 2020 guidelines (www.prisma-statement.org). The study was registered in PROSPERO (CRD42024622737).

2.2 PICO question and eligibility criteria

For this systematic review, the following criteria was applied according to PICO question: What is the effectiveness of non-fluoridated dentifrices and mouthwashes in the prevention of dental caries in children during mixed dentition period?

- Participants- Patients of age range 6-15 years
- Intervention- Introduction of one of the following oral care products containing biomimetic HAP, CPP-ACP, Chlorhexidine, Probiotics, Xylitol and Arginine as an active ingredient in dentifrices or mouthwash.
- Comparison- placebos and/or fluoridated dentifrices and mouthwashes.
- Outcome- to measure caries increment or change in bacterial colony count and change in pH of plaque and saliva.
- Inclusion criteria- Randomized Control Trials evaluating the efficacy of ingredients used in non-fluoridated dentifrices and mouthwashes in vivo. Studies in which participants had carious lesions in mixed dentition period (6-15 years), with ICDAS score 1 and 2, Streptococcus mutans colony count, DMFT/DMFS index and change in pH of plaque and saliva. Studies conducted between 2010-2024 and published in English language.
- Exclusion criteria- Literature, systematic and narrative reviews, in vitro studies, editorials and chapters. Randomized Control Trials based during primary dentition period and studies conducted on patients undergoing orthodontic treatment.

2.3 Information sources and search strategy

A systematic electronic search was done on various electronic search engines- PubMed, Google Scholar, The Cochrane Library, Embase, Web of Science database with the relevant search strategy using relevant key words and MeSH terms related to “non-fluoridated dentifrices”, “non-fluoridated mouthwash”, “prevention of dental caries in children”, “anticaries efficacy”, “mixed dentition” was applied along with AND/OR boolean operators. An additional manual search was performed by examining the reference lists of relevant studies and review articles. The search approach utilized both controlled vocabulary and free-text terms, initially designed for MEDLINE and subsequently adjusted for use with other databases.

2.4 Quality assessment and Data Synthesis-

The Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews for Interventions 5.1.0 was used to assess the risk of bias of every retrieved study included. The assessment tool included blinding of assessment, random sequence generation, selective reporting, incomplete outcome data, allocation concealment, and other plausible origins of bias to estimate the methodological constitution of studies included. Within every study, bias was sub-divided as “low risk of bias,” “high risk of bias” as well as “unclear risk of bias.” Cochrane Review Manager Version 5.4 (Cochrane library) was used to generate risks of bias Figures. The study characteristics were extracted according to the data extraction form prepared on Excel. The following data were recorded for each study: author, year, number of participants, age and follow up protocol, intervention, comparison and finally the outcome of study.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Study selection

A total of 2,381 articles were initially screened for relevance (Fig 1). Of these, 751 were identified as duplicate records. Records excluded (in vitro, animal, studies related to ortho patients) was 1574 outlined in the results table. Ultimately, 56 studies were selected for detailed evaluation under the inclusion and exclusion criteria, and 8 studies (19-26) were included in the final systematic review.

3.2 Study characteristics

The eight articles included in the review (Table 1) assessed a total of 2,785 participants, all of whom were reported as healthy by the study authors. All studies were randomized controlled trials conducted on children aged 6–15 years, with sample sizes ranging from 30 to 1,684 participants and study durations varying from baseline to up to two years. The delivery methods for the agents evaluated in the systematic review primarily included dentifrices and mouthwashes, except for one study where probiotic milk was provided to participants for rinsing in comparison to a fluoridated mouthwash (26).

Among the eight studies, one study each focused on Hydroxyapatite (19), Arginine (20), CPP-ACP (21), Xylitol (22) and Chlorhexidine (23). Additionally, one study evaluated a combination of Chlorhexidine and Probiotics (24) and two individual studies examined Probiotics (25,26).

3.3 Outcome of the studies

The outcome measures used included clinical assessment using International Caries Detection and Assessment System (ICDAS) criteria or DMFT/DMFS, clinical assessment of the count of number of colonies of *Streptococcus mutans* and *Lactobacilli* and the pH of plaque and saliva. Majority of studies showed no statistical difference in the count of number of colonies of *Streptococcus mutans*. Hydroxyapatite showed greater potential in lowering the count of primary cariogenic bacteria than fluoride group (19). Probiotic mouthwashes were found to be equally efficacious as compared to chlorhexidine and fluoridated mouthwash against bacterial load (25,26). Chlorhexidine alone has shown to be powerful agent in reducing bacterial count but when used with fluoride there was much more significant reduction in the levels of oral bacteria however the side effects were observed in more than 90% of the participants (23).

3.4 Risk of bias and quality assessment

Study conducted by Guglielmo Campus (19) and Malee (22) showed unclear risk of bias. While all the other studies (20,21,23,24,25,26) showed low risk of

bias (Fig 2). Randomization process of all the studies showed lowest risk of bias with 75%, while incomplete data was reported from the studies with highest risk of bias of 37.50% (Fig 3).

Study quality varied considerably, and out of a total possible Quality Assessment Tool for Studies with Diverse Designs QATSDD score of 42, scores for the individual studies ranged from 13 to 38. The average score was 29.1 (Fig 4). A mean score of 0 indicates none of the papers met any of the components of the criteria, with a total possible score of 3 indicating all the papers fully met the criteria. Some quality criteria were well addressed by the included studies, in particular the fit between the research question and method of data collection and analysis. None of the included papers had, however, evidence of user involvement in the design, and there was a lack of explicit theoretical framework underpinning the majority of the studies. Two other areas less well addressed were the approaches taken to estimate the sample size and assessment of reliability and validity of the measurement tools used. For the quality assessment, there was overall agreement between independent reviewers of 212 of 280 (75.7 %) of quality criteria scores. Because quality assessment was, however, an ordered variable, a weighted kappa was also carried out to establish relative concordance between reviewers. It was assumed that the differences between individual quality scores were equal. The inter-rater agreement (kappa with linear weighting) was 0.88 (95% CI, 0.74 –0.95) indicating substantial to perfect agreement.

Figure 1: Prisma Flow Chart

Studies (year)	Randomization process	Allocation concealment	Blinding of participants & personnel	Blinding of outcome	Incomplete outcome data	Selective reporting	Other Bias
Guglielmo Campus et al 2024	+	-	?	?	+	+	?
Arzu Aykut –Yetkiner et al 2014	?	?	?	?	-	?	?
Vijaya Lakshmi Bolla et al 2023	+	-	?	+	-	+	+
Krutika Y.Gedam et al 2022	+	+	+	-	?	-	?
Raju Umaji Patil et al 2019	+	+	+	+	+	?	+
Malee Arunakul et al 2011	?	+	?	?	+	+	?
Fatemeh Sadat Sajadi et al 2014	+	+	+	+	+	-	+
P.Kraivaphan et al 2013	+	?	?	+	-	+	+

Cochrane Risk of Bias Assessment (RoB 2)

?/yellow color: unclear risk of bias

-/red color: high risk of bias

+ /green color: low risk of bias

Figure 2: Risk of Bias Assessment

Figure 3: Overall Risk of Bias Assessment

Quality Criteria	Mean Score (SD, Range)
Evidence of user involvement in design	1.1 (0.7, 0-0.9)
Explicit theoretical framework	0.9 (0.5, 0.3-1.6)
Evidence of sample size considered in terms of analysis	1.8 (0.8, 0-3)
Statistical assessment of reliability and validity of measurement tools	1.9 (0.7, 1-3)
Strength and limitations critically discussed	2.1 (1.1, 0-3)
Good justification for method of analysis	1.9 (1.0, 0-3)
Clear description of research setting	2.4 (1.2, 1-3)
Description of procedure for data collection	2.2 (0.9, 1-3)
Statement of aims/objectives in body of report	2.4 (0.7, 1-3)
Detailed recruitment data	2.1 (1.1, 1-3)
Representative sample of reasonable size	2.7 (1.4, 1-3)
Rationale for choice of data collection tool	2.5 (0.9, 1-3)
Fit between research question and method of analysis	2.6 (1.2, 1-3)
Fit between research question and method of data analysis	2.5 (1.1, 1-3)

Figure 4: Quality Assessment of the Study

Table 1: Result Table

S. no	First author (year)	Participants (age) (follow-up protocol)	Intervention	Comparison	Outcome
1.	Malee Arunakul (2011)	80 subjects (8-9 years) (Baseline, 5 weeks and 10 weeks)	Group 1=Oral rinse of Xylitol (12.5% (w/v) for one min 3 times daily).	Group 2=0.05% (w/v) sodium fluoride. Group 3=0.05% (w/v) NaF + 12.5% (w/v) xylitol 3 times daily	Significant reduction in Streptococcus mutans (MS) counts was observed in participants using a mouthrinse containing 0.05% sodium fluoride (NaF) combined with 12.5% xylitol, compared to other groups, within 5 weeks and after 10 weeks. 12.5% xylitol reduced the MS counts after

				Group 4=Distilled water.	10 weeks compared to baseline significantly.
2.	P. Kraivaphan (2013)	1679/1693/1684 subjects (6-12 years) (Baseline, 1, 2 years)	Group 1=Arginine 1.5% + 1450 ppm Fluoride + Di-Calcium Phosphate. Group 2=Arginine 1.5% + 1450 ppm Fluoride + Calcium Carbonate.	Group 3=1450 ppm Fluoride + silica base used twice daily.	Toothpastes containing 1.5% arginine, an insoluble calcium compound, and 1,450 ppm fluoride demonstrated statistically significant reductions in DMFT increments (21.0% and 17.7%, respectively) and DMFS increments (16.5% each) compared to the control toothpaste ($p < 0.02$).
3,	Arzu Aykut-Yetkiner (2014)	60 subjects (13-15 years) (Baseline and 3 months)	Group 1=CPP-ACP (pea sized amount twice a day for 3 months).	Group 2=Fluoridated toothpaste (1450 ppm) (two times a day for 3 months).	In the both control and test groups, the mutans counts in the saliva were decreased in 3-month experimental period, which was found to be statistically significant ($p=0.000$ for both groups).
4.	Fatemeh Sadat Sajadi (2015)	120 subjects (12-14 years) (Baseline and 2 weeks)	Group 1=Chlorhexidine (10ml of 0.2% chlorhexidine gluconate used twice daily).	Group 2=0.2% sodium fluoride. Group 3=Fluoride-chlorhexidine (0.1% sodium fluoride and 0.2% chlorhexidine used twice daily).	No significant differences in <i>Streptococcus mutans</i> reduction were observed between all the groups ($P > 0.05$). However, a significant difference was found between mouthwashes containing Chlorhexidine and Chlorhexidine and Fluoride ($P = 0.0001$), indicating that the fluoride-chlorhexidine mouthwash was significantly more effective at reducing <i>S. mutans</i> compared to fluoride mouthwaalone but side effects were more noticed with the combination.
5.	Raju Umaji Patil (2019)	30 subjects (8-13 years) (Baseline and after 7 days)	Group 1=Probiotic rinse for 7 days.	Group 2=Fluoridated mouthrinse for 7 days.	The study demonstrated a significant reduction in both salivary <i>Streptococcus mutans</i> (SM) levels and Plaque Index (PI) scores in both groups by the end of the study period ($P < 0.001$). However, no significant differences were observed between the groups throughout the study.
6.	Krutika Y. Gedam (2022)	51 subjects (8-12 years age) (Baseline, 2 weeks and 4 weeks)	Group 1=Probiotic mouthrinse. Group 2=0.12% chlorhexidine (10 ml rinsed twice a day for period of two weeks).	Group 3=0.05% sodium fluoride (NaF) (rinsed twice a day for period of two weeks).	The mean reductions in colony counts using PB, CHX, and NaF mouthrinses were -1.0223 (-1.2201 to -0.8246), -0.9564 (-1.1503 to -0.7626), and -0.9511 (-1.1554 to -0.7467), respectively, all of which were statistically significant ($p < 0.0001$). However, intergroup comparisons showed no statistically significant differences in the mean change in colony counts ($p > 0.05$).
7.	Vijaya Lakshmi Bolla (2023)	150 subjects (6-15 years) (Baseline and 14 days)	Group 1=Probiotic mouthwash (10 ml rinsed for 1 min twice daily for 14 days).	Group 2=Placebo. Group 3=Kedodent Fluoridated mouthwash (10 ml rinsed for 1 min twice daily for 14 days).	Significant difference was observed in comparisons between baseline, immediate, and post-15-day intervention in Group Probiotic ($P < 0.001$) and Group Kedodent ($P < 0.001$). However, no significant difference was found in Group Placebo ($P = 0.846$).

8.	Guglielmo Campus (2024)	610 subject (4 to 5 and 6 to 7 years) (Baseline and 24 months)	Group 1= Hydroxyapatite toothpaste (HAF1000 and HAF1450)	Group 2=Monofluorophosphate fluoridated tooth pastes (F1000 and F1450)	The HAF1000 group demonstrated the greatest reduction in <i>Streptococcus mutans</i> levels, decreasing from 3.11 ± 1.13 at baseline to 2.00 ± 0.54 after a 2-year follow-up. Significant differences were observed in the mean minimum pH values following a sucrose challenge between the HAF and F groups, both for healthy/caries-free individuals (ICDAS 0) and those with caries lesions (ICDAS 1–6) using 1000 ppmF and 1450 ppmF toothpastes. However, statistically significant differences in the maximum pH decrease were found only in the 1000 ppmF group among children with caries.
----	-------------------------	--	--	--	--

4. DISCUSSION

The oral microbiota plays a crucial role in maintaining oral health by balancing the ecosystem within the mouth. Monitoring cariogenic bacteria levels in saliva or plaque helps assess cavity risk, while plaque pH measurement provides insight into the amount of acid produced in mouth. Proper oral hygiene and dietary choices influence these factors significantly. Salivary flow and buffering capacity also contribute to oral health by neutralizing acids, promoting enamel remineralization and clearing food debris, thus reducing the likelihood of dental caries.

Assessing plaque pH, salivary flow rate, and microbial composition helps evaluate caries susceptibility. These indicators, combined with clinical evaluations, enable dental professionals to determine caries risk accurately and develop personalized preventive strategies. Early monitoring also facilitates timely intervention, preventing or slowing down caries progression (19). Noninvasive treatments such as remineralizing agents are preferred for managing early lesions and preventing cavities. Fluoride is commonly delivered through dentifrices and mouthwashes. However, concerns about dental fluorosis in young children due to fluoride ingestion have led to recommendations to limit fluoride exposure. While guidelines are present regarding the size and amount of dentifrice to be used by children but some experts question whether even smaller doses effectively prevent cavities (9).

Fluoride is more effective on smooth surfaces but less so in pits and fissures. High-fluoride treatments pose risks, including fluorosis from excessive exposure and

some regions recommend limiting fluoride use for safety concerns. Given these issues, interest in non-fluoridated remineralizing agents has grown. An ideal remineralization agent should be able to penetrate subsurface layers or supply calcium and phosphate to these areas, avoid excessive calcium delivery and prevent calculus formation. It should function effectively in acidic conditions and support individuals with dry mouth along with enhancing the saliva's natural remineralization ability (27). This review examines the efficacy of non-fluoridated dentifrices and mouthwashes in preventing dental caries in children. Initially, the hypothesis suggested that these alternatives would not be as effective as fluoride-based products, but study findings contradicted this assumption. Non-fluoridated products successfully shifted the oral biofilm to a less cariogenic state. The dentifrices studied contained hydroxyapatite (HAP), casein phosphopeptide-amorphous calcium phosphate (CPP-ACP), and arginine, while mouthwashes featured probiotics, chlorhexidine, and xylitol. These agents were tested against either a placebo or fluoride for their ability to prevent caries in children aged 6 to 15 years. Studies were assessed based on DMFT/DMFS scores, ICDAS assessments, bacterial colony counts, and plaque pH measurements. All eight reviewed studies employed a parallel group design incorporating blinding, randomization, and allocation concealment. Study by Guglielmo Campus et al (19) examined HAP toothpaste's effects on plaque biofilm, featuring a large trial population, extended treatment duration, and long follow-up periods. Results suggested that HAP toothpaste lowered mutans streptococci levels, reducing acid production and slowing caries progression. It was seen that HAP interacts with tooth

surfaces and plaque to remineralize dentin and enamel. HAP functions as a gentle abrasive, releasing calcium and phosphate ions while buffering pH levels in cariogenic biofilms. Research by Shaw et al. found higher calcium and phosphorus levels in plaque from caries-free children, reinforcing HAP's role in oral health (28). Arginine, a semi-essential amino acid, is naturally present in saliva and metabolized by arginolytic bacteria through the Arginine Deiminase System. This process generates alkali, regulating cariogenic biofilms and enhancing enamel fluoride uptake. Unlike urea, arginine supplementation leads to alkaline environment. A two-year clinical study by P. Kraivaphan et al. found that dentifrices with 1.5% arginine, an insoluble calcium compound, and 1,450 ppm fluoride significantly reduced DMFT/DMFS scores compared to fluoride-only formulations (20).

CPP-ACP helps reduce demineralization and enhance remineralization. Under acidic conditions, ACP dissociates from CPP, increasing calcium and phosphate availability in saliva. CPP also prevents mineral precipitation, maintaining stable calcium levels. A study by Arzu et al. observed a reduction in *S. mutans* levels after three months of CPP-ACP use, supporting its antibacterial and buffering properties (21). Xylitol, a naturally occurring sugar alcohol, is commonly found in sugar-free gum and lozenges. Most oral bacteria cannot metabolize xylitol into acids, and studies show that it inhibits bacterial growth and adhesion. When combined with fluoride in mouthwashes, with research indicating a synergistic effect against *S. mutans* and *S. sobrinus*. A study by Malee et al. found that rinsing with 0.05% NaF and 12.5% xylitol significantly reduced salivary *S. mutans* levels within five weeks (22).

Chlorhexidine, a bisbiguanide on prolonged use can cause adverse effects such as staining, dry mouth, altered taste, irritation, and antimicrobial resistance (16). A study by Fatemeh et al. found significant reductions in *S. mutans* counts with fluoride-chlorhexidine mouthwash, though over 90% of participants experienced side effects (23). Probiotics are beneficial microorganisms that can survive in the acidic environment of tooth decay. Increasing clinical evidence supports their use in medical and dental applications. A study by Krutika et al. found that probiotic mouthrinse was as effective as

chlorhexidine and fluoride in reducing *S. mutans* levels in children aged 8 to 12 years (24). Another study by Vijaya et al. compared Kidodent, probiotics, and placebo, revealing that both Kidodent and probiotic mouthrinses effectively reduced *S. mutans* and lactobacilli levels (25). Similarly, Raju et al. (26) compared probiotics with fluoride mouthwash and found both significantly reduced caries-associated bacteria, suggesting that probiotics could help replace pathogenic microorganisms in the oral cavity. When probiotic was compared to fluoride mouthwash the results revealed a highly statistically significant difference ($P < 0.001$) between the mean salivary *S. mutans* counts and plaque index scores at baseline and on the 8th day in both groups. However, the intergroup comparison showed no statistically significant difference between the two groups, indicating that both were equally effective in reducing caries. This finding aligns with previous studies that compared *S. mutans* levels in saliva following the consumption of probiotic ice cream and yogurt. Therefore, probiotics may serve as an alternative approach for replacing pathogenic microorganisms with beneficial bacteria in the oral cavity (26). The above-mentioned findings reveal promising results as non-fluoridated alternatives demonstrate a significant potential in reducing caries incidence, indicating their viability as effective preventive measures. As most of the studies of non-fluoridated agents are either in vitro or done on children during primary dentition period, this review suggests researchers to perform more randomized controlled trials on non-fluoridated agents especially for age group of 6 years and above with more emphasis should be given towards the use of newer ingredients like hydroxyapatite, CPP-ACP, Xylitol and Probiotics.

Abbreviations:

AAPD: American Academy of Pediatric Dentistry; CPP-ACP: casein phosphopeptide amorphous calcium phosphate; DMF/DMFS: decayed, missing and filled teeth/decayed, missing and filled surfaces; HAP: Hydroxyapatite; ICDAS: international caries detection and assessment system.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I sincerely thank my guide Dr. Mousumi Goswami, for her invaluable guidance and support. I also

appreciate my teachers, colleagues, seniors and juniors for their constant insights and assistance. Special thanks to my family and friends for their encouragement throughout this journey.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None.

REFERENCES

1. Biria, M., Iranparvar, P., Fatemi, S. M., Nejadian, M., & Eslamiamirabadi, N. (2021). In vitro effects of three fluoride-free pastes on remineralization of initial enamel carious lesions. *Pediatric Dentistry*, 43(5), 389–395.
2. Sebastian, R., Paul, S. T., Azher, U., & Reddy, D. (2022). Comparison of remineralization potential of casein phosphopeptide: Amorphous calcium phosphate, nano-hydroxyapatite and calcium sucrose phosphate on artificial enamel lesions: An in vitro study. *International Journal of Clinical Pediatric Dentistry*, 15(1), 69.
3. Vyavhare, S., Sharma, D. S., & Kulkarni, V. K. (2015). Effect of three different pastes on remineralization of initial enamel lesion: An in vitro study. *Journal of Clinical Pediatric Dentistry*, 39(2), 149–160.
4. Vranic, E., Lacevic, A., Mehmedagic, A., & Uzunovic, A. (2004). Formulation ingredients for toothpastes and mouthwashes. *Bosnian Journal of Basic Medical Sciences*, 4(4), 51.
5. Basch, C. H., & Kernan, W. D. (2016). Ingredients in children's fluoridated toothpaste: A literature review. *Global Journal of Health Science*, 9(3), 1.
6. Kasemkhun, P., & Rirattanapong, P. (2021). The efficacy of non-fluoridated toothpastes on artificial enamel caries in primary teeth: An in vitro study. *Journal of International Society of Preventive and Community Dentistry*, 11(4), 397–401.
7. Detsomboonrat, P., Trairatvorakul, C., & Pisarnaturakit, P. P. (2016). Similar 1-year caries increment after use of fluoride or non-fluoride toothpaste in infants and toddlers. *Fluoride*, 49(3), 313.
8. American Academy of Pediatric Dentistry. (2023). Fluoride therapy. *The Reference Manual of Pediatric Dentistry* (pp. 352-358). American Academy of Pediatric Dentistry.
9. Limeback, H., Enax, J., & Meyer, F. (2021). Biomimetic hydroxyapatite and caries prevention: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Canadian Journal of Dental Hygiene*, 55(3), 148.
10. Elgamily, H., Safwat, E., Soliman, Z., Salama, H., El-Sayed, H., & Anwar, M. (2019). Antibacterial and remineralization efficacy of casein phosphopeptide, glycomacropeptide nanocomplex, and probiotics in experimental toothpastes: An in vitro comparative study. *European Journal of Dentistry*, 13(3), 391-398.
11. Al-Batayneh, O. B., Al-Rai, S. A., & Khader, Y. S. (2020). Effect of CPP-ACP on Streptococcus mutans in saliva of high caries-risk preschool children: A randomized clinical trial. *European Archives of Paediatric Dentistry*, 21, 339-346.
12. Haghgoo, R., Ahmadvand, M., & Moshaverinia, S. (2016). Remineralizing effect of topical NovaMin and nano-hydroxyapatite on caries-like lesions in primary teeth. *The Journal of Contemporary Dental Practice*, 17(8), 645–649.
13. Bijle, M. N., Ekambaram, M., & Yung Yiu, C. K. (2020). A scoping review on arginine in caries prevention. *The Journal of Evidence-Based Dental Practice*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jebdp.2020.101470>
14. Syed, M., Chopra, R., Shrivastava, V., & Sachdev, V. (2016). Comparative evaluation of 0.2% chlorhexidine mouthwash, xylitol chewing gum, and combination of 0.2% chlorhexidine mouthwash and xylitol chewing gum on salivary Streptococcus mutans and biofilm levels in 8-to 12-year-old children. *International Journal of Clinical Pediatric Dentistry*, 9(4), 313.
15. Gavarraju, D. N., Kallam, S. S., Avula, S. S., Sattenapalli, C. M., Audipudi, A. V., & Prathigudupu, R. S. (2023). Applicability of a natural nano-derivative as a mouth rinse on salivary pH and S. mutans count: An ex vivo study. *World*, 14(3), 208.
16. Krupa, N. C., Thippeswamy, H. M., & Chandrashekar, B. R. (2022). Antimicrobial efficacy of xylitol, probiotic, and chlorhexidine mouth rinses among children and elderly population at high risk for dental caries - A

- randomized controlled trial. *Journal of Preventive Medicine and Hygiene*, 63(2), E282–E287.
17. Wang, Y., Li, J., Sun, W., Li, H., Cannon, R. D., & Mei, L. (2017). Effect of non-fluoride agents on the prevention of dental caries in primary dentition: A systematic review. *PLoS ONE*, 12(8), e0182221.
18. Gunasekaran, S., Sakthivel, S., Nainan, P. I., & Shanthala, B. M. (2022). Non-fluoride remineralizing agent for caries prevention in children: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Oral Research and Review*, 14, 71–79.
19. Campus, G., Cocco, F., Wierichs, R. J., et al. (2024). Effects of hydroxyapatite-containing toothpastes on some caries-related variables: A randomized clinical trial. *International Dental Journal*, 74(4), 754–761.
20. Yin, W., Hu, D. Y., Li, X., Fan, X., Zhang, Y. P., Pretty, I. A., Mateo, L. R., Cummins, D., & Ellwood, R. P. (2013). The anti-caries efficacy of a dentifrice containing 1.5% arginine and 1450 ppm fluoride as sodium monofluorophosphate assessed using quantitative light-induced fluorescence (QLF). *Journal of Dentistry*, 41(Suppl 2), S22-S28.
21. Aykut-Yetkiner, A., Kara, N., Ateş, M., Ersin, N., & Ertuğrul, F. (2014). Does casein phosphopeptide amorphous calcium phosphate provide remineralization on white spot lesions and inhibition of *Streptococcus mutans*? *Journal of Clinical Pediatric Dentistry*, 38(4), 302–306.
22. Arunakul, M., Thaweboon, B., Thaweboon, S., Asvanund, Y., & Charoenchaikorn, K. (2011). Efficacy of xylitol and fluoride mouthrinses on salivary *Mutans streptococci*. *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Biomedicine*, 1(6), 488–490. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2221-1691\(11\)60106-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2221-1691(11)60106-8)
23. Sadat Sajadi, F., Moradi, M., Pardakhty, A., Yazdizadeh, R., & Madani, F. (2015). Effect of fluoride, chlorhexidine and fluoride-chlorhexidine mouthwashes on salivary *Streptococcus mutans* count and the prevalence of oral side effects. *Journal of Dental Research, Dental Clinics, Dental Prospects*, 9(1), 49–52. <https://doi.org/10.15171/joddd.2015.010>
24. Gedam, K. Y., & Katre, A. N. (2022). Efficacy of probiotic, chlorhexidine, and sodium fluoride mouthrinses on *Mutans Streptococci* in 8- to 12-year-old children: A crossover randomized trial. *Lifestyle Genomics*, 15(1), 35–44.
25. Bolla, V. L., Jyothi, M., Mettu, S. R., et al. (2023). Effectiveness of three mouth rinsing agents against *Mutans Streptococcus* and *Lactobacillus* species - A comparative study. *Annals of African Medicine*, 22(3), 365–372.
26. Patil, R. U., Dastoor, P. P., & Unde, M. P. (2019). Comparative evaluation of antimicrobial effectiveness of probiotic milk and fluoride mouthrinse on salivary *Streptococcus mutans* counts and plaque scores in children – An in vivo experimental study. *Journal of Indian Society of Pedodontics and Preventive Dentistry*, 37, 378–382.
27. Goswami, M., Saha, S., & Chaitra, T. R. (2012). Latest developments in non-fluoridated remineralizing technologies. *Journal of Indian Society of Pedodontics and Preventive Dentistry*, 30(1), 2-6.
28. Paszyńska, E., Pawińska, M., Gawriolek, M., Kamińska, I., Otulakowska-Skrzyńska, J., Marczuk-Kołada, G., Rzatowski, S., Sokołowska, K., Olszewska, A., Schlagenhauf, U., May, T. W., Amaechi, B. T., & Łuczaj-Cepowicz, E. (2021). Impact of a toothpaste with microcrystalline hydroxyapatite on the occurrence of early childhood caries: A 1-year randomized clinical trial. *Scientific Reports*, 11(1), 2650. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-81889-0>
29. Wright, J. T., Hanson, N., Ristic, H., Whall, C. W., Estrich, C. G., & Zentz, R. R. (2014). Fluoride toothpaste efficacy and safety in children younger than 6 years: A systematic review. *The Journal of the American Dental Association*, 145(2), 182–189.
30. Subramaniam, P., & Nandan, N. (2011). Effect of xylitol, sodium fluoride and triclosan containing mouth rinse on *Streptococcus mutans*. *Contemporary Clinical Dentistry*, 2(4), 287–290. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0976-237X.91790>

HOW TO CITE: Mriganka Kumar Phukan*, Mousumi Goswami, Sandhya, Ajay Khanna, Anticaries Efficacy of Non-Fluoridated Dentifrice and Mouthwashes Used in Children: A Systematic Review, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, 1 (12), 1050-1060. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18018199>

